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Research Article

Unlocking Precision: Exploring Molecular Diagnostic Methods for Enhanced Disease Detection

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ABSTRACT

Infectious diseases are a major global cause of morbidity and mortality, seriously affecting public health and socioeconomic stability. Since infectious diseases can be caused by a wide variety of pathogens with similar clinical manifestations and symptoms that are difficult to accurately distinguish, selecting the appropriate diagnostic techniques for the rapid identification of pathogens is crucial for clinical disease diagnosis and public health management. However, traditional diagnostic techniques have low detection rates, long detection times and limited automation, which means that they do not meet the requirements for rapid diagnosis. Despite the growth of molecular diagnosis from the era of Hippocrates, the emergence of COVID-19 is still remarkable. The previously used molecular techniques were not rapid enough to screen a vast population at home, in offices, and in hospitals. Additionally, these techniques were only available in advanced clinical laboratories. The pandemic outbreak enhanced the urgency of researchers and research and development companies to invent more rapid, robust, and portable devices and instruments to screen a vast community in a cost-effective and short time. There has been noteworthy progress in molecular diagnosing tools before and after the pandemic. Recent years have seen continuous developments in molecular detection technology, which has a higher sensitivity and specificity, shorter detection time and increased automation, and performs an important role in the early and rapid detection of infectious disease pathogens. The present study summarizes recent progress in molecular diagnostic technologies such as PCR, isothermal amplification, gene chips and high-through put sequencing for the detection of infectious disease pathogens, and compares the technical principles, advantages and disadvantages, applicability and costs of these diagnostic techniques. This review focuses on the awareness of molecular diagnostic. Nucleic acid testing is the cornerstone of modern molecular diagnostics. This review describes the status and future directions

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of molecular diagnostics, focusing on four major techniques: polymerase chain reaction (PCR), next-generation sequencing (NGS), isothermal amplification methods such as recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), and clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)-based detection methods. We explore the advantages and limitations of each technique, describe how each overlap with or complement other techniques, and examine current clinical offerings. This review provides a broad perspective into the landscape of molecular diagnostics and highlights potential future directions in this rapidly evolving field.

INTRODUCTION

Awareness of molecular diagnostic means understanding the purpose, techniques, applications, and importance of molecular methods used to detect diseases at the genetic or molecular level. Diagnostic methods are essential tools in modern medicine, used to identify diseases, monitor health status and guide treatment decisions. Raising awareness about these methods empowers individuals to seek timely medical care and improves overall health outcomes [3, 4]. Molecular diagnosis is a cutting-edge field in medical science that uses molecular biology techniques to identify diseases at the genetic, DNA, RNA or protein level. Unlike traditional, diagnostic methods that rely on observable symptoms or microscopy, molecular diagnostic offers precise, rapid, and early detection significantly improving patient outcomes [3, 5]. Molecular diagnostics is a collection of techniques used to analyze biological markers in the genome and proteome; these cells express their genes as proteins, applying molecular biology to medical testing. In medicine the technique is used to diagnose-monitor disease, detect risk, and decide which therapies will work best for individual patients. Advance and in agricultural bio security similarly to monitor crop - livestock disease, estimate risk, and decide what quarantine measures must be taken [11]. By analyzing the specifics of the patient and their disease, molecular

diagnostics offers the prospect of personalized medicine. These tests are useful in a range of medical specialties, including infectious disease, oncology, human leukocyte antigen typing (which investigates and predicts immune function) coagulation and pharmacogenetics the genetic prediction of which drugs will work best. They overlap with clinical chemistry (medical tests on bodily fluids).As molecular diagnostics has evolved; it has demonstrated clear advantages over some traditional methods, although it does not completely replace other methods The extreme sensitivity of molecular methods is crucial for directly detecting viral nucleic acids, making them a vital tool in diagnosing infections. When a pathologist states that patients have undetectable virus, that does not mean that they have no virus in their systems. It means that the level of virus is below the limits of detection for the assay used. A highly sensitive and robust assay delivers more valuable insights, enabling accurate diagnoses and informed treatment decisions. Other advantages are that molecular assays often require minimal sample volumes and do not require culture. Molecular methods offer high accuracy in detecting viruses by targeting specific DNA or RNA sequences, making them a reliable choice for diagnosis. Finally, molecular diagnostics usually offers tremendous time savings in the laboratory, allowing clinicians earlier access to data and thus earlier treatment for patients .Nucleic acid amplification is the key to molecular diagnostics. A molecular test for a virus must detect a specific RNA or DNA sequence during a tremendous amount of other nucleic acids: human genomic DNA, mRNA, bacterial DNA, and RNA. This process is like pulling the proverbial needle out of the haystack. The power of a nucleic acid amplification technique is that it can amplify a specific sequence and do so in a predictable manner so that the number of molecules in the initial sample can be quantified. Polymerase chain

reaction (PCR) is the gold standard for amplification processes in diagnostics. Since the technique was first published in 1985, it has become the most widely used nucleic acid amplification technology. With PCR, a target sequence of nucleic acid is amplified through a repetitive series of reactions catalyzed by a single enzyme, a thermal stable nucleic acid polymerase. PCR can amplify both DNA and RNA.

The process of PCR typically involves taking the sample through three different temperatures, each of which causes a different event. The sample is placed into a tube with the proper primers, thermal stable polymerase, nucleotides, and buffers. In the first step, denaturation by heating to 95°C causes the double-stranded DNA to form single strands. In the second step, the temperature is dropped to 55°C to 60°C, which allows the target specific primer to bind to only the intended nucleic acid sequence. The specificity of an assay depends on the quality of primer choice. Finally, in a third step, the temperature of the reaction is raised to about 72°C and the polymerase synthesizes an identical copy of the target sequence, called an amplicon. The cycle is repeated many times through the three different temperatures. Everything occurs rapidly in a closed tube in a thermo cycling instrument. The progress in diagnostic medicine has been driven by collaborative efforts among universities, industries, governments, and private institutions, harnessing science and technology to improve healthcare outcomes.

MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTIC METHODS:

- It is a branch of medical testing that focuses on detecting and analyzing biological molecules
- Such as DNA and RNA, protein or metabolites to diagnose and monitor diseases

- A test that sequences a patient DNA and RNA for markers of potential further diseases
- By analyzing the specific of the patient and their diseases
- Molecular diagnostic is a field of laboratory medicine that focus on the detection and analysis of nucleic acid {DNA&RNA} to diagnose and monitor diseases detect guide treatment decisions
- These methods are highly specific, sensitive and often faster than traditional diagnostic approaches like culture or microscopic.

COMMON MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTIC METHODS:

1. Polymer chain reaction {PCR}
2. Next generation sequence {NGS}
3. Nucleic acid hybridization
4. Ligase chain reaction {LCR}
5. Gene expression analysis
6. DNA microarrays
7. CRISPR-based diagnostics
8. FISH {fluorescence in situ hybridization}
9. ELISA + Molecular hybridization combination

1. POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION:

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is a powerful molecular biology technique used to amplify (make many copies of) a specific DNA segment. It was developed by Kary Mullis in 1983, who later received the Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1993 for

this invention. PCR is widely used in research, diagnostics, forensics, and biotechnology [1].

STEPS INVOLVED IN PCR: [1, 2]

A. Denaturation (94–98°C): The double-stranded DNA separates into single strands.

B. Annealing (50–65°C): Primers bind (anneal) to the complementary sequences on the single-stranded DNA.

C. Extension (72°C): DNA polymerase synthesizes new DNA strands by adding nucleotides to the primers.

FIGURE: 1 PROCEDURE FOR POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION

2. NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCE:

Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), also known as high-throughput sequencing, is a modern DNA sequencing technology that allows millions of DNA fragments to be sequenced simultaneously and rapidly. It represents a major advancement over traditional Sanger sequencing, offering faster, cheaper, and more accurate genome analysis [6, 7].

STEPS INVOLVED IN NGS:

A. Sample Preparation: DNA or RNA is extracted and fragmented into smaller pieces.

B. Library Preparation: Special adapters are attached to the DNA fragments to enable sequencing.

C. Amplification: DNA fragments are amplified (using PCR or bridge amplification) to create clusters for detection.

D. Sequencing: Each nucleotide added during synthesis emits a fluorescent signal, which is detected and recorded.

E. Data Analysis: The raw sequence data is processed by software to align, map, and interpret the sequences.

FIGURE: 2 INSTRUMENT USED IN NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCE

3. NUCLEIC ACID HYBRIDIZATION:

Nucleic acid hybridization is a molecular technique used to detect, identify, or study specific DNA or RNA sequences based on the principle of base pairing. It relies on the ability of complementary nucleic acid strands to bind, or hybridize, to each other under suitable conditions [3].

STEPS INVOLVED IN NAH:

- A. Denaturation:** The double-stranded DNA is heated or treated chemically to separate it into single strands.
- B. Hybridization:** The labelled probe is added, allowing it to bind to the complementary target sequence.
- C. Washing:** Non-specific bindings are removed.
- D. Detection:** The hybridized probe is detected using a radioactive, fluorescent, or enzymatic label.

FIGURE: 3 PROCESS OF NUCLEIC ACID HYBRIDIZATION

4. LIGASE CHAIN REACTION (LCR):

Ligase Chain Reaction (LCR) is a molecular diagnostic technique used to detect specific DNA sequences and point mutations. It is similar to PCR

but instead of amplifying DNA through polymerase activity, it uses a DNA Ligase enzyme to join two adjacent DNA probes that perfectly match the target sequence [3].

STEPS INVOLVED IN LCR:

A. Denaturation: The first step in PCR involves heating the DNA sample to 94-98°C, causing the double-stranded DNA to unwind and split into two single strands

B. Hybridization: Four synthetic oligonucleotide probes are added — two for each strand — that bind to adjacent sequences on the target DNA.

C. Ligation: DNA Ligase enzyme joins the probes only if they are perfectly matched to the target sequence.

D. Thermal Cycling: The process is repeated (similar to PCR cycles) to exponentially increase the ligated products, which can then be detected.

FIGURE: 4 PROCESSES OF LIGASE CHAIN REACTION

5. GENE EXPRESSION ANALYSIS:

Gene expression analysis is a molecular biology technique used to study how genes are turned on or off in cells. It helps determine which genes are active, how much they are expressed, and under what conditions. This is important for understanding normal biological processes, disease mechanisms, and treatment responses [3, 5].

METHODS:

- **RT-PCR (Reverse Transcription PCR):** Converts RNA to and amplifies it to measure expression levels.

- **qPCR DNA (Quantitative PCR):** Measures gene expression in real-time with fluorescent dyes.
- **Microarray Analysis:** Uses thousands of DNA probes on a chip to study the expression of many genes simultaneously.
- **RNA Sequencing (RNA-Seq):** A Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) method that provides detailed information about all RNA molecules in a sample.

FIGURE: 5 PROCEDURE FOR GENE EXPRESSION ANALYSIS

6. DNA MICROARRAYS:

DNA microarrays, also called gene chips or DNA chips, are powerful molecular biology tools used to study the expression of thousands of genes simultaneously. They allow scientists to analyze which genes are active or inactive in a cell or tissue under specific conditions [3].

STEPS INVOLVED IN DNA MICROARRAYS:

A. Preparation of Microarray: Thousands of known DNA sequences (probes) are immobilized on a small chip.

B. Sample Preparation: mRNA is isolated from cells and converted into cDNA, labelled with fluorescent dyes.

C. Hybridization: The labelled cDNA is applied to the microarray, where it binds to complementary probes.

D. Washing and Scanning: Unbound cDNA is washed off, and a laser scanner measures the fluorescence intensity.

E. Data Analysis: Computer software interprets fluorescence patterns to determine which genes are expressed and at what levels.

FIGURE: 6 PROCEDURE FOR DNA MICROARRAYS

7. CRISPR-based diagnostic:

CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) is a gene-editing technology originally discovered as part of the bacterial immune system. Beyond genome editing, CRISPR has recently been adapted as a powerful molecular diagnostic tool for detecting nucleic acids from pathogens, mutations, and genetic diseases [8].

TYPES:

A. SHERLOCK (Specific High Sensitivity Enzymatic Reporter Unlocking):

- Uses Cas13a to detect RNA targets.
- Highly sensitive and can detect viruses like Zika or SARS-CoV-2.

B. DETECTR (DNA Endonuclease-Targeted CRISPR Trans Reporter):

- Uses Cas12a to detect DNA targets.

- Commonly applied for detection of HPV and COVID-19.
- Based on Cas12b for rapid detection of nucleic acids.

C. HOLMES (One-Hour Low-cost Multipurpose Highly Efficient System):

FIGURE: 7 PROCESS FOR CRISPR-based diagnostic

8. FISH (fluorescence in situ hybridization):

Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH) is a cytogenetic technique used to detect and localize the presence or absence of specific DNA or RNA sequences on chromosomes or in cells using fluorescently labelled probes [9].

STEPS INVOLVED ON FISH:

A. Sample Preparation: Cells or tissue sections are fixed on slides.

B. Denaturation: Double-stranded DNA is denatured to single strands.

C. Hybridization: Fluorescently labeled probes bind to complementary DNA sequences.

D. Washing: Removes unbound probes.

E. Detection: Fluorescent signals are viewed under a fluorescence microscope.

FIGURE: 8 PROCESS OF FISH (fluorescence in situ hybridization)

9. ELISA: [Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay]

ELISA is a biochemical technique used to detect and quantify antigens (proteins, peptides, hormones) or antibodies in a sample such as blood or serum. It is one of the most commonly used immunological assays in diagnostics, research, and biotechnology [10].

STEPS INVOLVED IN ELISA:

A. Coating: The antigen or antibody is attached to a solid surface (usually a microtiter plate).

B. Blocking: Non-specific binding sites are blocked to prevent background noise.

C. Binding: The sample containing the target antigen or antibody is added to the plate.

D. Detection: A specific enzyme-linked antibody is added to form a complex.

E. Substrate Addition: A chromogenic substrate (e.g., TMB) is added; the enzyme catalyses a reaction that produces colour.

F. Measurement: The colour intensity is measured using a spectrophotometer.

FIGURE: 9 PROCEDURE FOR ELISA

AIM & OBJECTIVES:

- The main aim of the present work was to give awareness about molecular diagnostic methods among the public.

Here are the main objectives of molecular diagnostic methods:

- Early and Accurate Disease Detection:**

Identify diseases at the molecular or genetic level before clinical symptoms appear

- Pathogen Identification:**

Detect and differentiate microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites) with high specificity and sensitivity.

- Genetic and Hereditary Disorder Diagnosis:**

Identify mutations, chromosomal abnormalities, or genetic predispositions to inherited diseases.

- Cancer Diagnosis and Prognosis:**

Detect tumor markers, genetic alterations, and molecular signatures for cancer classification, staging, and risk assessment.

Support selection of targeted therapies based on genetic/molecular profiles of patients.

- **Monitoring Treatment Response:**

Evaluate the effectiveness of therapies by tracking molecular changes or minimal residual disease.

- **Infectious Disease Control:**

Enable rapid outbreak detection, epidemiological tracking, and antimicrobial resistance monitoring.

METHODOLOGY:

- **Needs Assessment**

Identify the target group (students, clinicians, lab technicians, patients, policymakers). Assess their current knowledge level and gaps.

- **Information Development**

Prepare accurate, up-to-date educational content on:

- Basic principles of molecular diagnostics
- Applications (infectious diseases, cancer, genetic disorders, etc.)
- Advantages and limitations
- Cost-effectiveness and accessibility

- **Awareness Strategies**

- Workshops and Training Programs: Hands-on demonstrations in labs.

- Seminars/Webinars: Expert lectures on new technologies and applications

- Printed Materials: Brochures, posters, booklets, guidelines.

- Digital Platforms: E-learning modules, social media campaigns, YouTube explainers.

- Community Outreach: Hospital awareness camps, diagnostic awareness days.

- **Practical Demonstrations**

- Show PCR, RT-PCR, sequencing, or point-of-care tests in practice.

- Case studies highlighting successful diagnosis through molecular methods.

- **Feedback and Evaluation**

- Conduct pre- and post-awareness surveys to measure improvement in knowledge.

- Collect feedback for refining future awareness programs.

RESULTS:

1) BASED ON AGE OF PUBLIC (214 RESPONSES):

TABLE: 1 BASED ON AGE OF PUBLIC

AGE	RESPONSES
18 YEARS	10.7% (23)
19 YEARS	24.8% (53)
20 YEARS	26.2% (56)
21 YEARS	9.8% (21)
22 YEARS	6.1% (13)

The lowest % is 22 years old & highest is 20 years persons.

FIGURE: 10 the following bar chart represents the age of public (214)

2) BASED ON GENDER OF PUBLIC (214 RESPONSES):

TABLE: 2 BASED ON GENDER OF PUBLIC

GENDER	RESPONSES
Female	119[55.6%]
Male	85[39.7%]

FIGURE: 11 The following bar chart represents the gender of public (214)

3) BASED ON OCCUPATION OF PUBLIC (214 RESPONSES):

TABLE: 3 BASED ON OCCUPATION OF PUBLIC

OCCUPATION	RESPONSES
Health care professional persons	56.1% (111)
Other persons	31.8% (72)
Researcher persons	12.1% (31)

FIGURE: 12 Pie chart represents the occupation of public (214)

4) Educational background of public (214):

TABLE: 4 Educational background of public (214)

Educational background	RESPONSES
Undergraduate persons	62.6%
Postgraduate persons	22%
PHD \ Others	16.1%

FIGURE: 13 Pie chart represents the educational background of public (214)

BASED ON SURVEY CONDUCTED IN PUBLIC:

1. Have you heard of molecular diagnostic before?

- Yes -37.3%
- No - 31.3%
- Not sure - 31.3%

1. Have you heard of molecular diagnostics before?
214 responses

FIGURE: 14 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

2. Which of the following do you associate with molecular diagnostics?

- DNA/RNA Testing - 55.6% (119)
- PCR - 47.7% (102)

- Genetic testing -29.9% (64)
- Covid 19 -24.3% (52)
- Blood sugar tests -21% (45)
- Not sure -10.7% (23)

FIGURE: 15 The following bar chart represents the results of 214 public responses

3. How did you first learn about molecular diagnostic methods?

- Internet -16.8%
- Healthcare provider -13.6%
- News/media -11.2%
- Others -34.1%
- Colleague -18.7%

3. How did you first learn about molecular diagnostic methods?
214 responses

FIGURE: 16 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

4. What is the main purpose of molecular diagnostics methods?

- Identify genetic disorder - 24.3%
- Determine drug resistance -12.6%
- Not sure -8.4%
- All the above - 29%
- Detect infectious diseases - 25.7%

4. what is the main purpose of molecular diagnostics tests?
214 responses

FIGURE: 17 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

5. Which of the following are molecular diagnostic techniques?

- ELISA -54.2% (116)
- RT-PCR -32.7% (70)
- CRISPR -28.5% (61)
- WESTERN BLOT -29% (62)
- NGS - 26.2% (56)
- NOT SURE - 13.1% (28)

FIGURE: 18 The following bar chart represents the results of 214 public responses

6. How confident are you in your understanding of molecular diagnostic methods?

- Somewhat confident -36.9%
- Not very confident - 30.4%
- Very confident - 17.3%
- Not at all confident -15.4%

FIGURE: 19 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

7. Do you think molecular diagnostics play an important role in modern medicine?

- Agree -31.8%
- Neutral -29.4%
- Strongly agree -26.2%
- Disagree - 12.6%

7. Do you think molecular diagnostics play an important role in modern medicine
214 responses

FIGURE: 20 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

8. In your opinion, which fields benefit most from molecular diagnostics?

- | | | | |
|--|--------------|---|--------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Infectious diseases | - 37.9% (81) | <input type="checkbox"/> Prenatal screening | - 24.3% (52) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cancer detection | -51.4% (110) | <input type="checkbox"/> Personalized medicines | -29% (62) |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> Biotechnology | -17.8% (38) |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> Others | -13% (28) |

8. In your opinion, which fields benefit most from molecular diagnostics? (select all that apply)
214 responses

FIGURE: 21 The following bar chart represents the results of 214 public responses

9. Would you consider taking a molecular diagnostic test if recommended by a health care provider?

- | | | | |
|------------------------------|--------|--|---------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes | -40.2% | <input type="checkbox"/> Maybe | -36.4% |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> Depends on the cost | - 12.1% |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> No | - 11.2% |

9. Would you consider taking a molecular diagnostic test if recommended by a healthcare provider?
214 responses

FIGURE: 22 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

10. What are the barriers to using or understanding molecular diagnostic?

- Lack of awareness - 53.7% (115)
- High cost - 27.6% (59)
- Limited access - 29.9% (64)
- Lack of trust in technology - 20.1% (43)
- Complex scientific language - 16.4% (35)
- Others - 13.1% (28)

10. what are the barriers to using or understanding molecular diagnostics? (select all that apply)
214 responses

FIGURE: 23 The following bar chart represents the results of 214 public responses

11. What would improve public awareness and acceptance of molecular diagnostics?

- Educational campaigns - 39.3%
- Health care provider - 21.5%
- Media awareness - 14.5%
- Others - 13.1%

11. What would improve public awareness and acceptance of molecular diagnostics?

214 responses

FIGURE: 24 Pie chart represents the results of 214 public responses

CONCLUSION

Molecular diagnostics has emerged as a transformative field in modern medicine, offering rapid, sensitive, and highly specific tools for the detection and monitoring of infectious diseases. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted both the limitations of traditional diagnostic approaches and the urgent need for portable, cost-effective, and scalable molecular technologies. Techniques such as PCR, next-generation sequencing (NGS), isothermal amplification methods (RPA, LAMP), gene chips, and CRISPR-based assays have significantly advanced pathogen detection, enabling earlier diagnosis, improved patient outcomes, and more effective public health management. Despite these advances, awareness and accessibility of molecular diagnostics remain moderate, particularly outside specialized laboratories. While young and educated individuals in health-related fields demonstrate growing recognition of its importance, there is still a gap in detailed knowledge and widespread application. Bridging this gap requires targeted education, training programs, and outreach initiatives to ensure that both healthcare professionals and the general public understand and utilize these technologies effectively. Ultimately, molecular diagnostics not only strengthens the fight against infectious diseases but also paves the way for personalized medicine,

agricultural biosecurity, and broader applications across clinical specialties. Continued innovation, collaboration among research institutions and industries, and enhanced public awareness will be essential to fully realize the potential of molecular diagnostics in improving global health outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Mullis K, Faloona F. Specific synthesis of DNA in vitro via a polymerase-catalyzed chain reaction. *Methods Enzymol.* 1987; 155:335–50.
2. Saiki RK, Gelfand DH, Stoffel S, Scharf SJ, Higuchi R, Horn GT, et al. Primer-directed enzymatic amplification of DNA with a thermostable DNA polymerase. *Science.* 1988;239(4839):487–91.
3. Luthra R, Medeiros LJ. Molecular diagnostics in pathology practice: a review. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2004;128(11):1186–94.
4. van Goor H, van der Vliet JA, van der Wal AC, van der Wal JE, van der Wal AM. Molecular diagnostics: current techniques and applications. *Clin Chem Lab Med.* 2005;43(6):555–65.
5. Schrijver I, Aziz N, Farkas DH, Furtado M, Gonzalez AF, Greiner TC, et al. Opportunities and challenges associated with clinical diagnostic genome sequencing: a report of the

- Association for Molecular Pathology. *J Mol Diagn.* 2012;14(6):525–40.
6. Shendure J, Ji H. Next-generation DNA sequencing. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2008;26(10):1135–45.
 7. Mardis ER. Next-generation sequencing platforms. *Annu Rev Anal Chem.* 2013;6:287–303.
 8. Doudna JA, Charpentier E. The new frontier of genome engineering with CRISPR-Cas9. *Science.* 2014;346(6213):1258096.
 9. Tkachuk DC, Pinkel D, Kuo WL, Weier HU, Gray JW. Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH): application in cancer diagnosis. *Cancer Invest.* 1991;9(4):347–58.
 10. Engvall E, Perlmann P. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). *Immunochemistry.* 1971;8(9):871–4.
 11. Gaina G. Molecular diagnostics: current approaches and their clinical applications. In: Gaina G, editor. *Diagnostics.* London: IntechOpen; 2025. p. 1–116.

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